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THE IMPACT OF THE CRISIS SITUATION CAUSED BY THE COVID 19 VIRUS ON POPULATION BEHAVIOR AND PUBLIC HEALTH - CASE STUDY SERBIA

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Abstract: Crisis situations are those situations that disrupt the normal functioning of certain social groups and that affect the disruption of numerous social processes. The pandemic caused by the COVID 19 virus disrupted almost all social processes in Serbia, with a direct impact on the public health of the population. Public health functioning disorders generate a wide range of influences on other areas of social life. In that way, a circle of influences and disturbances is created, which cause the violation of the social community security. The perception of the population, the type of influences and their action is essential for prevention, ie taking protection measures. The paper deals with the research of the population perception and the impact on safe and secure life and the social community functioning. The first part of the paper presents the resilience of the social community in Serbia and the existing protection mechanisms against infectious diseases. After that, the impact of the pandemic on public health was presented, as well as the perception of danger in certain categories of respondents depending on numerous factors that influenced their behavior during the state of emergency and the epidemic caused by COVID 19. The research was conducted within the doctoral studies of the Faculty of Technical Sciences, University of Novi Sad, 765 respondents were surveyed.

Key words: crisis situations, public health, resilience, pandemic Covid 19

1. INTRODUCTION

There are numerous challenges, risks and threats that modern states face from their inception to the present day. Regardless of the level of technical and technological progress and development of a particular country, there are challenges, risks and threats that know no borders and that threaten the population around the world. One of the dangers that threatened almost all the countries of the world at the same time, which did not bypass the richest or the poorest, and which still lasts, has affected the population all over the planet. Culturally, politically, economically different countries, at one point, found themselves in a joint struggle with the same enemy. The pandemic caused by the COVID 19 virus did not bypass Serbia either, the first case of coronavirus in the country was recorded at the beginning of March 2020 and lasts until today. The same virus has affected all countries of the world, but what was different were the strategies in this fight, the economic power of the countries, the political

will of the heads of states, as well as the behavior of the population. It is characteristic that the behavior of the population ranged from completely uncertain, due to lack of information, to completely directed by the authorities. Accordingly, the situation with the number of infected, cured and deceased was different from place to place.

2. CRISIS SITUATIONS - CONDITIONS OF ORIGIN AND EFFECTS ON PUBLIC HEALTH

The term *crisis* is probably one of the most commonly used in everyday speech today. Although there is no agreement on its meaning, it is a very popular and widely used term. [1]

Paul t'Hart gives a modern definition of the crisis, stating that it is "an unpleasant event, which represent a challenge to decision makers, tempts them to act in conditions of threat, time pressure and unpreparedness." Crisis is "a serious threat to the basic structures or fundamental values and norms of the social system which, in conditions of time pressure and very uncertain circumstances, requires critical decisions." [12] This definition has two essential characteristics. Its significant advantage is that it can be applied to all types of disturbances (environmental threats, breakdowns of information and communication systems, economic crises, conflicts within countries, prison riots, regional wars, factory explosions and natural disasters). This characteristic causes a multidisciplinary approach to understanding crises. Second, this definition directs our attention to decision-making: crises are seen as an opportunity to make critical decisions.

Modern crises exceed the management capacities of national governments and require the engagement of supranational structures. In addition, they do not know national borders, and their complexity exceeds the efforts of governments to understand their causes, anticipate their development and the best ways to prevent their occurrence, ie to mitigate their consequences. [8] The modern crisis is not limited to a certain area or sphere of politics (eg health care, or economy) but moves from one area to another, digging up problems and (re)combining them into unpredictable mega-threats. Modern crises are not even precisely timed in the sense that the time of their beginning and end is clearly known, since these are immanent vulnerabilities that arise, fade, mutate and attack again. Therefore, modern crises are a special challenge for national governments, ie decision makers. [7,8]

As pointed out, the essence of the crisis is that the normal process in a given social system is disrupted. Researchers of different types of crises have identified a whole range of factors that can cause such disorders. Most researchers of crises (and catastrophes) agree that today's crises cannot be explained only in a monocausal way, but also by listing a few easily recognizable factors. Their origin can be in natural, social and technical-technological phenomena, or in their combination. [1] This set of factors can also be classified according to different levels of the system. Factors and causes of crises are different, but what is common to all crises is the impact on the protected values of a particular community and the consequences they leave, endangering the economy, life and human health, which directly affects the public health. [2]

A very important factor of prevention, as well as an adequate response to the crisis situation, is the security culture of the population. It is the product of individual and group values, attitudes, perceptions, competencies and patterns of behavior that determine commitment to the health and well-being of the community.

Responding to the crisis is a serious challenge. [5] A crisis requires critical decisions that must be made in changing and difficult circumstances. At the same time, the crisis generates obstacles to the quality decision-making process. Common problems multiply exponentially during a crisis. Crisis managers must solve complex dilemmas without the information they need in an unstable organizational environment and in conditions of serious stress. [3]

Crisis and emergency situations produce numerous negative consequences for all the protected values of a society. In addition to numerous natural and technical-technological risks and dangers that threaten our society and that have affected our country in the past few years, epidemics and pandemics are one of the dangers that has become a dominant danger in a very short time with very serious consequences not only for population health but also for the economy of our country. [6] The pandemic caused by the COVID 19 virus directly endangered human life and health, and indirectly left numerous other negative consequences to all spheres of social life. At the beginning of the pandemic, the oldest population and the most health-sensitive groups of people with certain autoimmune diseases and minor or major health problems were most endangered, while now there are more and more young people with a more severe clinical picture. The public health of the population is seriously endangered, and the health care system has been put to a difficult test.

3. PUBLIC HEALTH AND RESISTANCE OF THE POPULATION TO INFECTIOUS DISEASES

The resilience of a social community, above all, depends on its readiness to respond to threat. [11, 10] The same is the case with individuals, ie the population, there are numerous factors that affect the response and reaction in a certain crisis or emergency situation. The pandemic caused by the COVID 19 virus directly endangered the health of the population. The indirect impact of the pandemic is much greater and affects all areas of social life, and causes many other long-term consequences. The magnitude of the consequences that manifests directly depends on the readiness of the population or the state to confront the existing danger, whether it is about preparedness in terms of knowledge about a particular area or some previous experience and prevention measures taken.

When we talk about the existing mechanisms of prevention and protection, since 2016, with the adoption of the Law on Public Health and the Law on Protection of the Population from Infectious Diseases, Serbia has begun normative regulation of this area by taking the first steps in preventing and protecting the population from infectious diseases. However, a number of other actions need to be taken to ensure that these protection mechanisms have full effect and are fully implemented.

The Law on Public Health of the Republic of Serbia defines **public health** as a set of knowledge, skills and activities aimed at improving health, disease prevention and control, prolonging and improving the quality of life through organized measures of society. Areas of public health activity are [14]: physical, mental and social health of the population; health promotion and disease prevention; environment and population health; working environment and population health; organization and functioning of the health system; dealing with crisis and emergency situations.

Implementation of public health in the field of crisis and emergency situations includes:

- 1) public health risk assessment in relation to crisis and emergency situations;
- 2) acting in accordance with the law governing the handling of crisis and emergency situations and the national response program of the health sector in crisis and emergency situations in cooperation with the competent authorities and services;
- 3) development of protection and rescue plans and plans for dealing with crisis and emergency situations;
- 4) providing and exchanging information in crisis and emergency situations, in accordance with the law and action plans.

According to the Law on Protection of the Population from Infectious Diseases, an **infectious disease** is a disease caused by a specific causative agent resulting from the transmission of an agent or its toxic products from an infected person or other reservoir to a susceptible host, either directly from person to person or indirectly through contaminated food, water, objects of general use, transient host, vector or inanimate environment, and exchange of fluid contaminated with the causative agent.

This law regulates protection of the population from infectious diseases and special health issues, determines infectious diseases that endanger the health of the population of Serbia and whose prevention and suppression is of general interest to Serbia, implementation of epidemiological surveillance and measures, their implementation and provision of funds for their implementation, supervising the implementation of this law, as well as other issues of importance for protection of the population from infectious diseases.

The current pandemic has shown the great vulnerability of the Serbian health care system. Existing protection mechanisms against this infectious disease have been used in accordance with the available capacities. At the time of the danger, the health care system showed a great lack of equipment and material resources, as well as health workers. However, in accordance with the needs and the development of the epidemiological situation, numerous health means and equipment were procured, health care personnel were redeployed to the necessary places, and at the same time a large number of new health workers were employed. New Covid hospitals were also built, all with the aim of increasing the openness of the society. In addition to the health problems of the population, numerous other life and work activities are endangered and disturbed. The behavior of the population and their perception of danger depended on a number of factors. In order to determine the extent to which this current pandemic, and in what way, disrupts work and overall life activities of the population and in what way it affects public health, a research was conducted at the level of doctoral studies at the Faculty of Technical Sciences, University of Novi Sad.

4. THE AIM OF THE WORK

The aim of the study was to determine the impact of danger on public health, the impact on daily activities of the population, their life and work obligations, as well as the perception of danger by respondents depending on many factors such as age, gender, education, location and way of living, work and other factors. The survey is focused on the experience of respondents with emergencies and what are the situations that the population perceives as emergencies.

5. METHODOLOGICAL APPROACH

The research was conducted within the doctoral studies of the Faculty of Technical Sciences, University of Novi Sad in the field of: Risk management of catastrophic events and fires, subject Public Health in Emergencies and Crisis Situations.

The research methodology is adapted to the situation and is based on voluntary participation, an anonymous questionnaire and appropriate statistical processing. The request for filling in the questionnaire was sent through certain communication channels: e-mail, viber, whatsapp, facebook and the like.

6. SUMMARY OF RESEARCH RESULTS

The survey, in which 765 people participated, was dominated by females, 60% of the total number of respondents were females. The largest number of respondents is between 26 and 46 years old. Almost a third of the respondents are between 26 and 35 years old. 40% of respondents have higher education. One fifth of the respondents live in the countryside (22%),

while the rest of the respondents live in the city (78%). More than half of the respondents live in apartments, 55% of them.

It was observed whether this pandemic had a greater impact on older or younger population, whether men or women, residents living alone or those living in families with a larger number of members felt more vulnerable. Did the level of education have an impact on the perception and behavior of the population.

Did the place of residence have an impact on the residents' perception of this danger, did it have a greater impact on people living in the countryside or in the city, in the house or apartment. Have there been major changes in living and working activities in urban or rural areas due to the epidemic.

Whether the performance of daily work activities and tasks and to what extent was endangered, which activities were most affected and whether the employees managed to successfully respond to their work tasks in the conditions of this pandemic.

How and to what extent did certain categories of the population respect the recommended measures of the crisis headquarters, and which were the reasons for non-compliance with the applied measures. As well as how satisfied they were with the work of state bodies and services. How they communicated and how they were informed about the existing danger.

7. DISCUSSION

The current pandemic, as a representative of contemporary crises, has shown its comprehensiveness when it comes to spatial planning. Easy and fast expansion prevents adequate action of national authorities. When the threat spills over the national border, the affected state is practically unable to fully act on it, and the reaction of the state is almost always conditioned by the reaction and behavior of other states. During the fight against the pandemic caused by COVID 19 virus, those slightly more prepared, more orderly, economically more powerful countries had a slight advantage in response to the virus. While other countries are still dealing with the problems of how to organize society in this situation, how to continue living and working activities with as few human victims and economic consequences as possible, richer and economically stronger countries, in addition to daily measures and activities taken to prevent the spread of the epidemic, they used part of their capacities and redirected to finding a vaccine in order to take big steps against this danger. Of course, the question always arises as to whether they are motivated by economic gain or the general public health of the world community.

Practice in Serbia, in the fight against this pandemic, has shown that much more action is needed to reduce vulnerability and increase the resilience of the population to various risks and dangers. The researching results showed that this still current pandemic had a great impact on the life and work activities of the respondents. Almost all social groups are affected by this pandemic. The researching results indicate that the residents in the older years respected the imposed measures more and listened to the instructions, unlike the middle-aged residents where were certain violations. The epidemic affected the daily routine of family life, but also the performance of professional activities. The population in rural areas had less fear of transmitting the virus. Since the use of the Internet has multiplied, communication has been maintained through telephone and social networks. The importance of communication and information has also increased, due to the fear for life.

The magnitude of impact of danger on a certain category of inhabitants and their behavior depended on several factors, on the type of work and activity they are engaged in, on age and lifestyle and other factors. Great efforts are needed to fully implement and take advantage of

existing protection measures, increase public awareness of importance of prevention and constant education and dissemination of knowledge about existing potential threats.

The importance of crisis management when it comes to pandemics is evident. Given that the emergence and development of the COVID-19 pandemic is a surprise for the authorities and professional services, the development of a crisis management system is justified. In practice, it has been shown that it is necessary that persons performing the function of management at all levels of government and among decision-makers should have an education that includes elements of crisis management, which is not the case in the process of managing this pandemic.

8. CONCLUSION

Although the pandemic was and is a current challenge for the country's health system, it has affected other systems and represents a challenge to which many countries have adapted in different ways and taken activities and measures with different approaches. The complexity of the crisis situation is reflected in the impact of the pandemic on various aspects of social life, which has resulted in significant consequences. This research indicates the need to take care of the population in crisis situations, especially the most vulnerable groups, and to devise new modalities for response.

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